

Audit Firm Characteristics and Earnings Management among Listed Consumer Goods Firms Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of audit firm characteristics on earnings management among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Using an ex-post facto research design, the study analyses panel data obtained from audited financial statements and annual reports of eighteen purposively selected firms covering the period 2015–2023. The investigation focuses on five key audit firm attributes of audit report lag, audit independence, audit firm size, audit firm tenure, and audit firm rotation and evaluates their influence on earnings management, measured through discretionary accruals from the Modified Jones model. The study employs panel estimated generalize least squares regression estimation technique. The findings reveal that audit report lag and audit firm size have no significant effect on earnings management, implying that the timing of audit completion and the perceived reputational strength of larger audit firms do not serve as major deterrents to managerial manipulation of earnings. Conversely, audit independence shows a significant negative effect on earnings management, underscoring the importance of auditor autonomy, objectivity, and professional scepticism in ensuring credible financial reporting. Furthermore, both audit firm tenure and audit firm rotation demonstrate significant positive effects on earnings management. This suggests that prolonged auditor–client relationships and potential transitional gaps associated with mandatory rotation may increase opportunities for earnings manipulation. The study concludes that qualitative audit firm characteristics particularly independence, tenure, and rotation are fundamental determinants of earnings management practices in Nigeria’s consumer goods sector. Overall, the research provides valuable insights for regulators, policymakers, and audit practitioners by highlighting the need to strengthen auditor independence, monitor tenure duration, and manage rotation processes to enhance audit quality and promote greater financial reporting transparency in emerging markets.

Keywords: Earnings management, Audit independence, Audit tenure, Discretionary accruals, Audit quality

JEL Classification: G30; M41; M42

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1. Introduction

The integrity, transparency, and reliability of financial reporting constitute foundational pillars for effective capital market operations and informed decision-making by investors, creditors, regulators, and other stakeholders (El-Hawary & Hassouna, 2021; Ugbah, 2024). Central to safeguarding this integrity is the external audit function, which provides independent assurance that financial statements fairly represent a firm's financial performance and position, free from material misstatement (Ibrahim et al., 2022). Despite its importance, the audit function has faced scrutiny due to recurring corporate scandals, raising doubts about its effectiveness in detecting or deterring manipulative financial reporting practices (Ayinla et al., 2022; Yayangida et al., 2023). Notable failures, such as the collapses of Enron and WorldCom in the United States, and cases involving Cadbury Nigeria Plc and distressed Nigerian deposit money banks, highlight that external audits do not always constrain opportunistic managerial behavior (Kajola et al., 2021; Oladejo, 2020). These occurrences have intensified debates on whether audit firm characteristics genuinely enhance audit quality and mitigate earnings manipulation (Francis, 2011).

Earnings management (EM) has emerged as a central concern in this discourse. Defined as the intentional manipulation of financial reporting outcomes through accounting estimates or real activities, EM can mislead users regarding a firm's underlying economic performance or influence contractual outcomes dependent on accounting metrics (Dechow et al., 1995; Oshodin & Ogiewa, 2022). In Nigeria's consumer goods sector, an industry critical for economic growth, industrial development, and employment pressures to meet profit expectations, maintain dividend consistency, and project stability in a competitive and inflation-prone environment heighten incentives for EM (Akombende & Chukwu, 2023; Okolie, 2014; Umar et al., 2019). Empirical evidence shows heterogeneity in EM practices among Nigerian consumer goods firms, underscoring persistent financial reporting concerns in the sector (Abubakar et al., 2020; Oyeleye, 2025).

The effectiveness of external audits in curbing EM is influenced by specific audit firm attributes, including audit report lag, auditor independence, audit firm size, audit tenure, and audit firm rotation (Udofia & Ebiaghan, 2025). Audit report lag indicates the timeliness of audit completion; excessively long lags may signal complex accounting issues, while abnormally short lags may reflect insufficient audit rigor (Habib et al., 2013; Ilaboya & Ohiokha, 2014). Auditor independence, often proxied by audit fees, remains debated: higher fees may indicate greater audit effort (Chituru et al., 2022; Martinez & Moraes, 2016) but may also imply economic dependence that compromises objectivity (Eriabie & Eriabie, 2017). Evidence from Nigeria reflects this duality, producing positive, negative, and insignificant outcomes (Ajibike et al., 2022; Santos-Jaén, 2025).

Audit firm size, typically distinguishing Big 4 from non-Big 4 auditors, is associated with superior audit quality due to expertise, resources, and reputational incentives (Francis & Yu, 2009). Yet Nigerian studies reveal mixed results, suggesting institutional factors, regulatory enforcement, and

industry characteristics may moderate the Big 4 advantage (Alzoubi, 2017; Oyeleye, 2025; Yasar, 2013). Audit tenure also presents a trade-off: longer tenure enhances client-specific knowledge and audit quality (Bappah et al., 2024; Myers et al., 2003), but prolonged engagements may erode independence and increase familiarity threats (Breuer & Schutt, 2024; González-Díaz et al., 2015). Consequently, mandatory auditor rotation has been adopted in some jurisdictions, though empirical evidence on its effectiveness is mixed, with both improvements in audit quality and transitional challenges reported (Chi et al., 2009; Salehi et al., 2022).

A fundamental methodological challenge in EM research concerns measurement. The Modified Jones Model remains the most widely used for detecting discretionary accruals (Dechow et al., 1995; Istrate, 2024), but scholars highlight its susceptibility to measurement error and misclassification (Kothari et al., 2005; Dechow et al., 2010). Recent studies advocate for methodological refinements, including combined models and firm-specific controls to improve detection accuracy (Breuer & Schütt, 2024; Istrate, 2024).

Within Nigeria, consumer goods firms are particularly vulnerable to EM due to competitive pressures, fluctuating input costs, and market expectations, as evidenced by financial scandals such as Cadbury Nigeria Plc (Okolie et al., 2013; Okpala & Adetunbi, 2024). Most Nigerian audit quality studies focus on the banking sector, leaving a gap in non-financial sectors (Ojo & Akinwunmi, 2020; Okechukwu & Ene, 2022). Emerging studies in consumer goods firms reveal inconsistent EM patterns and varied effectiveness of audit firm characteristics, warranting sector-specific investigation (Izevbekhai et al., 2022; Oyeleye, 2025).

Despite extensive scholarly attention, literature remains fragmented. Some studies report that larger audit firms, higher independence, and longer tenure constrain EM (Gul et al., 2017; Jادیappa et al., 2021; Muhammad, 2024), while others find contradictory or insignificant results (Lawrence et al., 2011; Kurawa & Ishaku, 2020; Orbunde et al., 2021). This study is situated within the Nigerian consumer goods sector over a recent and extended period (2015–2023), thereby capturing post-regulatory dynamics, evolving audit market conditions, and contemporary earnings management practices that earlier studies may not fully reflect. This enhances the relevance and timeliness of the findings in light of recent corporate governance reforms. While prior studies have extensively examined audit firm characteristics, this study extends the literature by incorporating a more integrated perspective on audit quality dimensions and their interaction in shaping financial reporting outcomes. In particular, audit independence is proxied by the natural logarithm of audit fees to capture economic dependence between auditors and clients, while audit report lag is emphasized as a key timeliness indicator reflecting audit efficiency and reporting discipline, both of which may influence the extent of earnings management. The study also considers audit firm size, tenure, and rotation, alongside discretionary accruals derived from the Modified Jones model (Kothari et al., 2005), and applies a panel estimation framework that accounts for firm-specific heterogeneity. Collectively, these refinements demonstrate that the study goes beyond replication

by providing deeper insights into how audit firm characteristics jointly influence earnings management in an emerging market context.

The objective of the study is therefore to examine the effect of audit firm characteristics—specifically audit report lag, audit independence (proxied by log of audit fees), audit firm size, audit firm tenure, and audit firm rotation—on earnings management among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Accordingly, the study is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the literature review; Section 3 outlines the methodology; Section 4 discusses the empirical results and findings; while Section 5 provides the conclusion and policy recommendations.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Earnings management

Earnings management refers to the deliberate use of managerial discretion in accounting choices and operating decisions to influence reported earnings. It involves actions taken within, or sometimes outside, the boundaries of acceptable accounting standards to achieve desired financial-reporting outcomes (Dechow & Skinner, 2000; Ozeolo et al., 2025). Managers may engage in earnings management to meet market expectations, maximise performance-based compensation, avoid debt-covenant violations, or manage regulatory and political pressures.

Two major forms are commonly highlighted in the literature. Accrual-based earnings management (AEM) involves manipulating accounting estimates such as provisions, depreciation, or revenue recognition without altering underlying cash flows. Real earnings management (REM), on the other hand, affects actual business activities—for example, offering sales discounts, overproducing to reduce cost of goods sold, or cutting discretionary expenses (Ayinla et al., 2022; Roychowdhury, 2006).

Empirical studies typically measure earnings management through discretionary accruals. Widely used models include the Jones (1991) model, the Modified Jones model (Dechow et al., 1995), and the performance-matched approach of Kothari et al. (2005). Among these, the Modified Jones model often augmented with performance matching is considered more reliable for detecting abnormal accruals. Accordingly, this study adopts discretionary accruals derived from the Modified Jones model as the measure of earnings management.

2.1.2 Audit firm characteristics

Audit firm characteristics refer to the features of external auditors that influence audit quality and enhance the credibility of financial reports (Jameel et al., 2024; Djajanti, 2025). In this study, they are measured through audit report lag (timeliness of audit completion), auditor independence (objectivity in financial reporting), audit firm size (Big 4 vs. non-Big 4 as a quality proxy), audit tenure (duration of the auditor–client relationship), and audit firm rotation (periodic change of audit firms to reduce familiarity risk). These attributes are widely recognized for their role in constraining earnings management and promoting transparent reporting.

2.1.2.1. Audit Report Lag

Audit report lag is the time between a firm's fiscal year-end and the date the independent auditor signs the audit report (Ozeolo et al., 2025). It is a key indicator of reporting timeliness, which enhances the relevance of financial information for decision-making (Djajanti, 2025). Shorter lags suggest efficient audits, while longer lags may signal complex accounting issues, auditor–management disputes, or scrutiny triggered by potential earnings management (Lambert et al., 2017; Habib & Huang, 2019; Luypaert et al., 2016; Fakhfakh & Jarboui, 2022). Audit lag is measured in calendar days and often log-transformed to address skewness.

2.1.2.2. Auditor independence

Auditor independence refers to the auditor's ability to carry out audit responsibilities objectively and without undue client influence (Frankel et al., 2002). It encompasses independence in mind, which reflects intellectual honesty and professional skepticism (Ibrahim et al., 2022), and independence in appearance, which concerns stakeholders' perceptions of the auditor's objectivity (Abdel-khalik, 2002; Bryan, 2020; ElHawary & Hassouna, 2021). Independence may be threatened by economic ties such as the provision of non-audit services, high audit fees, and long auditor tenure, which can create self-review and familiarity risks (Li & Len, 2005; European Commission, 2011; Khalil, 2022). Common proxies include non-audit fee ratios, fee dependence, tenure, and Big 4 affiliation (Umar et al., 2019; Nelwan et al., 2021).

2.1.2.3. Audit firm size

Audit firm size is widely regarded as a key determinant of audit quality, as larger firms possess greater expertise, advanced technology, and stronger incentives to protect their reputation (Khalil, 2022; Santos-Jaen, 2025). Big 4 firms—PwC, Deloitte, EY, and KPMG—are particularly associated with higher audit credibility due to their extensive resources and professional expertise (Imade, 2021; Erasmus & Micah, 2021). Empirical evidence is mixed: some studies report that large firms reduce earnings management (Lopes, 2018; Okolie, 2014), while others find no significant effect (Inua & Okoh, 2018). Audit tenure also influences quality, with long relationships potentially impairing independence (Carey & Simnett, 2006; Kautsar & Bety, 2023) or enhancing audit effectiveness (Myers et al., 2003; Monroe & Hossain, 2013; Ajibike et al., 2022).

2.1.2.4. Audit firm tenure

Audit firm tenure refers to the number of consecutive years an audit firm serves a client (Okolie, 2014; Akrawah et al., 2020). Longer tenure improves audit quality through accumulated client-specific knowledge and stronger detection of reporting irregularities (Myers et al., 2003). However, extended relationships may impair independence due to over-familiarity and reduced skepticism (Carcello & Nagy, 2004; Djajanti, 2025). Empirical findings are mixed: some studies highlight learning benefits (Tyokoso et al., 2016; Imade, 2021), while others link long tenure to increased earnings management (Yusuf, 2020; Zgarni & Chikhaoui, 2022). Regulatory bodies such as the EU and PCAOB advocate rotation to mitigate familiarity risks (European Commission,

2011; PCAOB, 2011; Jadiyahpa et al., 2021). Tenure is commonly measured in years (Myers et al., 2003; Syamsu et al., 2023).

2.1.2.5. Audit firm rotation

Audit firm rotation involves periodically changing a company's external auditor to strengthen independence and reduce familiarity threats (PCAOB, 2011; Bazerman et al., 2007; Mali & Lim, 2018). Advocates argue that rotation enhances objectivity and professional skepticism (Monroe & Hossain, 2013). Critics contend that new auditors face steep learning curves, higher costs, and potential reductions in audit quality (Bae et al., 2013; Kitiwong et al., 2017). Empirical evidence is mixed: some studies find no significant effect on earnings management (Kalanjati et al., 2019; Salehi et al., 2022), while others show possible negative consequences (Carey & Simnett, 2006; Chi et al., 2009; Ozeolo et al., 2025). Regulations vary, such as Nigeria's ten-year limit (NCCG, 2018).

2.2. Theoretical framework

This study is anchored on Agency Theory. Agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) posits that conflicts arise between shareholders (principals) and managers (agents), as managers may act opportunistically through practices such as earnings management. External auditors play a monitoring role in reducing these agency conflicts by mitigating information asymmetry between managers and shareholders. In this regard, audit firm characteristics such as audit report lag, audit independence, audit firm size, audit tenure, and audit rotation serve as important governance mechanisms that can constrain managerial discretion and improve financial reporting quality (Habib et al., 2013; Choi et al., 2010; Carey & Simnett, 2006). Accordingly, Agency Theory provides the theoretical justification for examining audit firm characteristics as key determinants of earnings management in Nigeria.

2.3. Empirical review

2.3.1. Audit report lag and earnings management

Audit report lag significantly influences earnings management (EM), though effects vary by context. Apalowowa et al. (2025) found a weak negative relationship between audit lag and earnings performance in Nigerian deposit money banks, emphasizing transparency despite limited direct impact. Bappah et al. (2024) reported that prolonged audit timelines in Nigerian consumer goods firms increase EM, providing managers with opportunities to manipulate earnings. Fakhfakh and Jarboui (2022) observed that upward earnings management accelerates audit reporting, whereas downward manipulation extends lag. Similarly, Habib and Huang (2019) linked long audit delays to poor reporting quality and heightened stock price crash risk, while Rahmawati (2018) found extended audit durations raise discretionary accruals. Lambert et al. (2017) cautioned that overly compressed deadlines may also undermine audit quality, highlighting the need for balanced audit timelines. Against this backdrop, it is therefore hypothesized that:

H₀₁: Audit report lag has no significant effect on earnings management among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

2.3.2. Audit independence and earnings management

Audit independence, often proxied by audit fees, shows mixed outcomes. Okonkwo et al. (2024) and Izevbekhai et al. (2022) reported that higher fees, reflecting compromised independence, increase EM in Nigerian conglomerates and non-financial firms. Conversely, Kajola et al. (2020) and Leeftang (2010) found that adequately compensated auditors enhance audit quality and constrain EM in Nigerian banks and Dutch firms. Kurawa and Ishaku (2020) observed positive but insignificant effects, suggesting that fees alone are insufficient, while Moraes and Martinez (2017) highlighted that abnormal fees in Brazil increase EM due to economic dependence. Based on the empirical evidence, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H₀₂: Auditor independence has no significant effect on earnings management among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

2.3.3. Audit firm size and earnings management

Audit firm size also affects EM, though evidence is context-dependent. Udofia and Ebiaghan (2025) found no significant effect on real EM in Nigerian service firms, while Izevbekhai et al. (2022) observed a positive association in non-financial firms. Studies in emerging markets, including Bui and Le (2021), Kurawa and Ishaku (2020), and Oyebamiji (2020), showed that larger audit firms reduce EM by leveraging reputation, resources, and expertise. Ajekwe and Ibiamke (2017) similarly reported that Big 4 auditors significantly constrain EM in Nigeria's real sector. On the basis of the empirical evidence, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H₀₃: Audit firm size has no significant effect on earnings management among listed consumer goods firm in Nigeria.

2.3.4. Audit firm tenure and earnings management

Audit tenure exhibits mixed effects. Olagunju et al. (2024) and Bappah et al. (2024) reported that longer tenure reduces discretionary accruals in manufacturing and consumer goods firms due to accumulated client knowledge. Tyokoso et al. (2016), Zayol et al. (2017), and Myers et al. (2003) highlighted similar benefits of moderate tenure. In contrast, Ogiriki and Williams (2023), Akombende and Chukwu (2023), Yusuf (2020), and Zgarni and Chikhaoui (2022) found longer tenure increases EM due to familiarity threats, while Carcello and Nagy (2004) emphasized potential independence impairment from extended engagements. Based on the empirical evidence, the following hypothesis is advanced:

H₀₄: Audit firm tenure has no significant effect on earnings management among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

2.3.5. Audit firm rotation and earnings management

Evidence on audit rotation is inconclusive. Udofia and Ebiaghan (2025) found no effect on real EM, whereas Olagunju et al. (2024) showed switching auditors reduces discretionary accruals. Okonkwo et al. (2022) and Salehi et al. (2022) observed increased EM following rotation, highlighting transitional risks. Chi et al. (2009), Carey and Simnett (2006), and Okolie (2014) reported rotation improves independence and reduces EM, while Jackson et al. (2008) and Cameran et al. (2016) cautioned that frequent rotation may disrupt audit quality. Overall, rotation's effectiveness depends on auditor competence, context, and complementary governance mechanisms. In light of the foregoing evidence, the following hypothesis is advanced:

H₀₅: Audit firm rotation has no significant effect on earnings management among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

3. Methodology

This study adopts an ex-post facto research design to examine the effect of audit firm characteristics on earnings management among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Secondary data were obtained from the audited annual reports of 18 purposively selected firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) over the period 2015–2023. The use of purposive sampling is justified by the relatively small population of listed consumer goods firms and the need to ensure inclusion of only firms with complete, consistent, and comparable financial data across the study period. Selection was therefore based on researcher judgment, focusing on firms with continuous listing status and uninterrupted availability of audited reports, thereby enhancing data reliability. Panel data extracted from the reports were analyzed in compliance with the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) Act (2011, 2018). The study employs panel estimated generalized least squares regression to estimate the impact of audit report lag, audit independence, audit firm size, tenure, and rotation on earnings management, proxied by discretionary accruals using the Modified Jones model, while accounting for cross-sectional and time-series variations.

3.1. Model Specification

This study adapts and modifies the model of Olagunju et al. (2024) to examine the effect of key audit attributes on earnings management in Nigerian consumer goods firms. The adapted econometric model is:

$$EM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ARL_{it} + \beta_2 AUDI_{it} + \beta_3 AFSIZ_{it} + \beta_4 AFTEN_{it} + \beta_5 AFROT_{it} + \mu_{it} \text{-----(1)}$$

Where: **EM** = Earnings Management (proxied by discretionary accruals from the Modified Jones model). Discretionary accruals were measured using the Modified Jones model (Kothari et al., 2005) to control for performance effects:

$$DA = TA_{i,t} - TA_{i,t-1} - \left[\delta_i \left(\frac{1}{AI_{i,t}} - a_1 \right) + \delta_{1,i} \left(\Delta REV_{i,t} - \Delta REC_{i,t} \right) + \delta_{2,i} \left(PPE_{i,t} - PPE_{i,t-1} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

Where: DA= Discretionary Accruals is used to measure Earning Management;
 TA_{it}= Total accruals for firm I in year t= Net Income-Operating cash flow;
 TA_{it-1}= Total accruals for firm I in year t,
 ΔREV_{it}=Change in net revenues for firm I in year t;
 ΔR_{it}= Change in accounts receivable for firm I in year t
 PPE_{it}= Property plant and equipment for firm I in year t;
 δ_i, δ₁, δ₂ are coefficient, t= time.

ARL = Audit Report Lag is the time between year-end and the SEC 90-day deadline. A long or positive lag suggests delayed reporting and possible lower audit efficiency, while a short or negative lag indicates timely reporting and stronger audit quality.

AUDI = Audit Independence (log of audit fees).

AFSIZ = Audit Firm Size (Big 4 vs. Non-Big 4).

AFTEN = Audit Firm Tenure (Audit firm tenure was measured by the number years an audit firm spend with a client before being changed.)

AFROT = Audit Firm Rotation (Audit Firm Rotation was measured by a dummy variable: “1” if audit firm is changed and “0” if the audit firm is not changed.).

β₀ – β₅ = Regression coefficients.

μ_{it} = Error term. The model enables empirical testing of how audit characteristics and firm-level controls influence earnings management in Nigerian consumer goods firms.

B₁, β₂, β₃, β₄, β₅ > 0

The above signifies the apriori expectation which shows a positive trend among the independent variables and brings about change in the dependent variables.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. Results

The descriptive statistics indicate variation in earnings management (EM) and audit characteristics among Nigerian consumer goods firms. EM, measured via discretionary accruals, has a mean of -0.1870 and shows extreme outliers (range: -7.4202 to 7.8412), negative skewness (-2.0392), and high kurtosis (16.8402), reflecting concentrated aggressive reporting by few firms. Audit report lag (ARL) has a mean value of -4.99 days with a standard deviation of 28.51, indicating that, on average, listed consumer goods firms complete and release their audit reports about five days before the SEC deadline. However, the relatively large standard deviation shows substantial variation across firms, with firms reporting well before the SEC deadline.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

	EM	ARL	AUDI	AFSIZ	AFTEN	AFROT
Mean	-0.1870	-4.9938	4.6127	0.7593	3.9136	0.0741
Median	0.0515	-5.0000	4.6532	1.0000	3.5000	0.0000
Maximum	7.8412	91.0000	5.3979	1.0000	9.0000	1.0000
Minimum	-7.4202	-64.0000	3.6532	0.0000	1.0000	0.0000
Std. Dev.	1.6259	28.5084	0.4069	0.4289	2.3496	0.2627
Skewness	-2.0392	0.4956	-0.2298	-1.2128	0.5248	3.2527
Kurtosis	16.8402	3.9160	2.3865	2.4709	2.2501	11.5800
Jarque-Bera	1405.2460	12.2962	3.9665	41.6043	11.2324	782.5707
Probability	0.0000	0.0021	0.1376	0.0000	0.0036	0.0000
Observations	162	162	162	162	162	162

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Audit independence, with an average value of 4.6127 (approximately ₦100.6 million in audit fees), indicates a balanced level of audit engagement across firms. This suggests that audit fees are sufficiently substantial to reflect meaningful audit effort and service intensity, while not being excessively high to imply extreme dependence on or undue reliance on external auditors. Big 4 auditors dominate the sample (AFSIZ mean = 0.7593), showing that most firms are audited by large international audit firms. Audit firm tenure averages 3.9136 years, suggesting moderate auditor–client relationships, while audit firm rotation is low (mean = 0.0741), indicating infrequent changes in external auditors over the period. Most variables deviate from normality, reinforcing the use of robust panel GLS regression to examine the impact of audit attributes on EM.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

	EM	ARL	AUDI	AFSIZ	AFTEN	AFROT
EM	1.0000					
ARL	-0.0039	1.0000				
AUDI	0.0781	-0.3860	1.0000			
AFSIZ	-0.0517	-0.4414	0.5892	1.0000		
AFTEN	-0.0008	0.1410	0.2346	0.0409	1.0000	
AFROT	0.0406	-0.0598	0.0370	0.0490	-0.3418	1.0000

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

The correlation matrix shows very weak relationships between earnings management (EM) and audit firm related variables. EM is nearly uncorrelated with audit report lag (ARL, -0.0039) and audit tenure (AFTEN, -0.0008), while audit independence (AUDI, 0.0781) and audit firm rotation (AFROT, 0.0406) exhibit slight positive associations. Audit firm size (AFSIZ, -0.0517) shows a minimal negative relationship, suggesting Big 4 auditors marginally constrain EM. Overall, correlations are weak, indicating that audit attributes' effects on EM are complex and context-dependent. Low correlations also imply minimal multicollinearity, supporting the suitability of subsequent Panel GLS regression for robust multivariate analysis.

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factor estimates

Variance Inflation Factors						
Variable	C	ARL	AUDI	AFSIZ	AFTEN	AFROT
Coefficient						
Variance	3.0159	0.0000	0.1761	0.1507	0.0039	0.2769
Centered VIF	NA	1.3579	1.7611	1.6741	1.3067	1.1539

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis indicates minimal multicollinearity among independent variables, with ARL = 1.3579, AUDI = 1.7611, AFSIZ = 1.6741, AFTEN = 1.3067, and AFROT = 1.1539, all well below the threshold of 5. This shows that each audit attribute—timing, independence, firm size, tenure, and rotation—provides unique information, ensuring stable regression coefficients. Consequently, the relationships with earnings management are reliable, and the risk of inflated standard errors or misleading inferences is negligible, allowing for meaningful interpretation of each variable's impact on discretionary accruals.

Table 4: Diagnostic Test Estimates

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:			
F-statistic	16.8719	Prob. F(2,154)	0.0000
Obs*R-squared	29.1168	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0000
Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH			
F-statistic	38.4623	Prob. F(1,159)	0.0000
Obs*R-squared	31.3601	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.0000
Ramsey RESET Test			
Specification: EM C ARL AUDI AFSIZ AFTEN AFROT			
	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	1.1987	155.0000	0.2325
F-statistic	1.4368	(1, 155)	0.2325
Likelihood ratio	1.4947	1.0000	0.2215

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Diagnostic tests show the regression model is correctly specified (Ramsey RESET: $t = 1.1987$, $p = 0.2325$), but serial correlation (Breusch-Godfrey: $F = 16.8719$, $p = 0.0000$) and heteroskedasticity (ARCH: $F = 38.4623$, $p = 0.0000$) are present. These issues could bias standard errors and reduce efficiency, justifying the use of Panel Estimated GLS to produce reliable and robust parameter estimates.

Table 5: Model Statistics Result

Weighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.5207	Mean dependent var	0.4548
Adjusted R-squared	0.4974	S.D. dependent var	1.4665
S.E. of regression	1.2246	Sum squared resid	208.4637
F-statistic	1.7898	Durbin-Watson stat	1.8546
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0232		

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

The model explains 52.1% of the variation in earnings management ($R^2 = 0.5207$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.4974$), indicating moderate explanatory power. It is statistically significant ($F = 1.7898$, $p = 0.0232$) with reasonable prediction accuracy ($SE = 1.2246$) and shows no serious autocorrelation issues (Durbin-Watson = 1.8546).

Table 6: Panel Estimated Generalize Least Square Estimates

Dependent Variable: EM				
Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section weights)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.2816	0.4615	2.7771	0.0062
ARL	0.0015	0.0015	0.9386	0.3496
AUDI	-0.3500	0.1079	-3.2430	0.0015
AFSIZ	0.0260	0.0763	0.3413	0.7334
AFTEN	0.0324	0.0086	3.7531	0.0003
AFROT	0.0867	0.0319	2.7211	0.0073

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

4.2. Test of Hypothesis

Based on the Panel EGLS results, hypotheses were tested at a 5% significance level. If p -value < 0.05 , the null is rejected; if p -value ≥ 0.05 , it is not rejected.

H01: Audit Report Lag (ARL)

ARL ($\beta = 0.0015$, $p = 0.3496$) is not significant. Audit report timing does not significantly affect earnings management, suggesting other factors like audit independence may be more influential.

H02: Audit Independence (AUDI)

AUDI ($\beta = -0.3500$, $p = 0.0015$) is significant. Higher audit independence reduces earnings management, improving financial reporting quality.

H03: Audit Firm Size (AFSIZ)

AFSIZ ($\beta = 0.0260$, $p = 0.7334$) is not significant. Auditor size (Big 4 vs. non-Big 4) has no significant effect on earnings management.

H04: Audit Firm Tenure (AFTEN)

AFTEN ($\beta = 0.0324$, $p = 0.0003$) is significant. Longer tenure increases earnings management, likely due to familiarity threats.

H05: Audit Firm Rotation (AFROT)

AFROT ($\beta = 0.0867$, $p = 0.0073$) is significant. Auditor rotation increases earnings management, possibly due to transitional gaps in oversight.

4.3. Discussion of findings

This study examined the effect of audit attributes on earnings management (EM) among listed Nigerian consumer goods firms. The findings are discussed in relation to the hypotheses, prior literature, theoretical perspectives, and a priori expectations.

Audit report lag (ARL) was found to have no significant effect on earnings management. This suggests that whether a firm submits its audit report early or late relative to the SEC's 90-day requirement does not meaningfully influence managerial opportunism. The result aligns with Apalowowa et al. (2025), who observed a weak link between audit timing and earnings performance in Nigerian banks, but contradicts studies by Bappah et al. (2024) and Rahmawati

(2018), which reported that delayed reporting increases EM. Agency theory suggests that timely reporting reduces information asymmetry, but in this sector, ARL alone appears insufficient to constrain opportunistic behavior, highlighting the importance of other governance mechanisms.

Audit independence (AUDI), proxied by audit fees, significantly reduced earnings management. Higher audit independence limits managerial opportunism, consistent with agency theory, which stresses independent monitoring to mitigate conflicts of interest. This supports Kajola et al. (2020) and Leeftang (2010), who found that greater auditor autonomy enhances audit quality, though contrasts exist with studies suggesting excessive fees may impair independence (Moraes & Martinez, 2017; Okonkwo et al., 2024). The finding confirms that adequately compensated, independent auditors effectively detect and deter earnings manipulation.

Audit firm size (AFSIZ) was not significant, indicating that being audited by a Big 4 or non-Big 4 firm does not materially affect EM. While some studies report that larger firms improve audit quality (Bui & Le, 2021; Oyebamiji, 2020), others show mixed results in Nigeria (Izevbekhai et al., 2022; Udofia & Ebiaghan, 2025). This suggests that firm size alone is insufficient to constrain opportunistic reporting without complementary factors like independence and tenure.

Audit firm tenure (AFTEN) positively influenced earnings management, supporting the familiarity threat hypothesis. Longer auditor-client relationships may reduce professional scepticism, enabling opportunistic reporting, consistent with Yusuf (2020) and Ogiriki and Williams (2023). Political cost theory also explains managers' use of extended tenure to manipulate earnings under regulatory scrutiny.

Audit firm rotation (AFROT) also positively affected EM, suggesting that changing auditors may create transitional gaps exploitable by managers. This aligns with agency theory, as disruptions in monitoring temporarily weaken controls, and corroborates studies by Salehi et al. (2022) and Kurawa and Ishaku (2020), which noted that rotation can inadvertently increase earnings manipulation in the short term.

Overall, audit independence constrains EM, while extended tenure and rotation increase opportunistic behavior. Audit report lag and firm size were insignificant, highlighting the need for stronger governance mechanisms, consistent with agency and political cost theories.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1. Conclusion

This study examined the effect of audit firm characteristics on earnings management (EM) among listed Nigerian consumer goods firms using an ex-post facto research design and panel data from eighteen purposively sampled firms over 2015–2023. The study focused on five audit attributes: audit report lag, audit independence, audit firm size, audit firm tenure, and audit firm rotation, with EM measured by discretionary accruals using the Modified Jones model.

Findings reveal that audit report lag and audit firm size do not significantly influence earnings management, suggesting that timeliness and auditor size alone are insufficient to constrain managerial opportunism. In contrast, audit independence significantly reduces EM, highlighting the critical role of auditor autonomy and adequate remuneration in enhancing financial reporting reliability. Audit firm tenure positively affects EM, indicating that prolonged auditor–client relationships may reduce scepticism and facilitate opportunistic reporting. Similarly, audit firm

rotation increases EM, likely due to transitional gaps and temporary inefficiencies during auditor handovers.

Overall, the study concludes that audit independence, tenure, and rotation substantially influence earnings management, while report lag and firm size are less determinative. These findings emphasize the need for a balanced approach to audit quality, prioritizing independence, monitoring tenure, and carefully managing rotation. The study contributes empirical evidence from the Nigerian consumer goods sector and offers practical insights for regulators, investors, and governance bodies to strengthen financial reporting transparency and mitigate managerial opportunism.

5.2. Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations are made:

- i. **Audit Report Lag:** Although not significant, firms should comply with regulatory deadlines to maintain transparency and investor confidence. Regulators should promote timely reporting as part of broader governance frameworks.
 - ii. **Audit Independence:** Companies should ensure that audit fees are clearly disclosed and set at levels that fully reflect the scope and complexity of audit work to prevent economic dependence on clients. Boards and regulators should enforce strict auditor independence requirements, actively monitor auditor–client relationships, and impose clear restrictions on conflicts of interest. Strengthening these controls will improve audit objectivity, reduce earnings management, and enhance financial reporting quality.
 - iii. **Audit Firm Size:** Firms should focus on auditor competence and quality rather than size or reputation. Regulatory assessments should emphasize qualitative audit performance.
 - iv. **Audit Firm Tenure:** The study recommends that firms reduce prolonged auditor–client relationships to limit familiarity threats, as longer audit tenure increases earnings management. Accordingly, audit engagements should not be continuously extended, and timely auditor changes should be ensured to strengthen independence and curb earnings management in listed consumer goods firms.
 - v. **Audit Firm Rotation:** Rotation policies should include robust transition planning and knowledge transfer to minimize disruption. Firms should prioritize incoming auditors' expertise, and regulators should structure rotations to balance independence with audit effectiveness.
- Overall, strengthening auditor independence, managing tenure, and carefully implementing rotation are key to reducing earnings management and enhancing financial reporting transparency in Nigerian consumer goods firms.

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